

PRINCIPLES, STAGES, SYSTEM OF INCLUSIVE EDUCATION AND THE IMPORTANCE OF PROFESSIONAL GUIDANCE IN IT

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15518598>

Abstract: This article discusses the principles, stages, and system of inclusive education, as well as the importance and effectiveness of guiding students to a profession within it, from a scientific and theoretical perspective.

Keywords: Inclusive education, Adaptation, Individual, Unchanging Empathy, Stereotyping, Reflection, Praise, Personal-psychological development, Adaptation.

Introduction.

Today, the reforms being implemented in our country prioritize human interests, and significant work is being done to help people feel the changes taking place in their lives. In particular, it is necessary to recognize the attention paid to the education system, in particular, reforms in the field of preschool education, general secondary education, professional and higher education. The issue of providing quality education to the younger generation is currently included in the priority strategy of our country, based on the principle of "For the dignity of man". President Sh. Mirziyoyev, explaining the concept of human dignity, emphasizes that "By human dignity, we understand the creation of decent living conditions and modern infrastructure for every citizen, the provision of qualified medical services, quality education, a social protection system, and a healthy ecological environment." It is worth noting that our President has declared 2023 the "Year of Attention to Humanity and Quality Education".

Because the quality of education and the development of society are inextricably linked, that is, if quality education is established, educated, competitive, and equipped with modern competencies will be produced, and such personnel will contribute to the development of society by making rational decisions in their professional and managerial activities. Today's education system has as its main goal the preparation of young people as worthy successors of our future. In this regard, the development of the regulatory and legal framework and content of inclusive education, aimed at providing equal education to children with disabilities, along with healthy young people, is becoming one of the priority tasks.

In this regard, on September 23, 2020, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Education” was adopted, which defined inclusive education as a form of education. Inclusive education is aimed at ensuring equal opportunities for all learners in educational organizations, taking into account the diversity of individual educational needs and individual capabilities, and is the organization of inclusive education in educational organizations for children (individuals) with physical, mental, sensory (sensory) or mental disabilities.

The issue of improving inclusive education in our republic has found its due reflection in many documents of our government, including in the speeches, reports and speeches, decrees and resolutions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev.

In particular, in order to improve the quality of education for young people with disabilities, the need for printed and audio books in various specialties and areas is studied every six months, and on this basis, a number of tasks are being set to form a list of literature, and to establish a system for publishing audio materials and Braille-based literature in subjects in the relevant specialties and areas of higher educational institutions. However, there are sufficient shortcomings in this regard.

In particular, the Resolution of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-4860 dated October 13, 2020 “On measures to further improve the system of education and upbringing of children with special educational needs” noted the main problems in this regard:

Some educational institutions that educate children with special educational needs do not provide an accessible environment and opportunities for them;

Educational institutions that educate children with special educational needs are not fully equipped with the necessary literature, methodological manuals, and equipment and facilities for training in various professions;

As a result of the lack of public awareness-raising activities about the right of children with special educational needs to receive education and the content and essence of the inclusive education system, parents do not have sufficient information about the possibility of educating their children with special educational needs in general education institutions;

Local executive authorities do not pay sufficient attention to solving problems related to involving children with special educational needs in inclusive education;

Subjects related to inclusive education methodology are not included in the curricula of higher educational institutions specializing in pedagogy;

The lack of inclusive education programs in textbooks on pedagogy and methodology, as well as the fact that future teachers do not undergo internships in educational institutions where children with special educational needs are involved, negatively affects the quality of their professional training.

The solution to these problems directly depends on the need to equip future teachers in higher educational institutions with knowledge, skills and qualifications related to the pedagogical and psychological laws of inclusive education, the content and principles of inclusive education.

This, in turn, requires the technical equipment of educational institutions and the introduction of special training courses for future teachers aimed at developing their interaction with people with disabilities, as well as the development of their didactic and methodological support. From this point of view, this textbook serves as one of the important didactic tools in preparing future teachers for inclusive education activities.

Main part

In the current period of socio-economic development, there are trends in the world to introduce and master new technologies into the educational process based on innovative educational platforms for joint education of healthy people and people with health problems in the classroom. In world educational practice, this direction is called inclusive education, and inclusion has also entered the practice of the educational process of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Raising children with special needs is one of the main tasks of our country. Today, our society has set itself the task of comprehensively supporting the rights of people with special needs, implementing their full-fledged education at all stages of this process.

In our opinion, the most optimal and effective direction for implementing this task is inclusive education. Inclusive education is a living organism, a living process, which implies a creative approach to the educational process by teachers and parents. After all, each child requires an individual approach, everyone has the right to receive education and recognition of their abilities in society.

The purpose of this article is to review the current state of work in this area in our republic, as well as to develop recommendations for further improving the inclusive education system in our country in order to implement inclusive education. Today, more than 700 thousand people with special educational

needs live in Uzbekistan, more than 100 thousand of whom are under the age of 16 (according to the Senate of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic).

In recent years, a number of positive reforms have been implemented at the state level in the field of the regulatory legal framework aimed at strengthening the rights and obligations of people with special educational needs in our republic. In particular:

1. In 2020, the Law “On the Rights of People with Special Educational Needs” [2] was adopted, which provides for preferential housing for people with special educational needs and benefits, education, employment, as well as full use of existing infrastructure, information and public services.

2. On June 7, 2021, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev signed the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. OPI-695 “On Ratification of the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Special Educational Needs” (New York, December 13, 2006) [3], which provides for the following:

Recognition of the rights of persons with special needs and their equal rights with others in all aspects of their lives. Taking this into account, it is envisaged to take appropriate measures to ensure that persons with special needs, under appropriate conditions and in accordance with the legislation, have access to support and decision-making mechanisms, including the restriction of the legal capacity of persons with special needs.

3. On October 13, 2020, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev No. 4860 “On measures to further improve the system of education and upbringing of children with special needs” was adopted.

The majority of professors and teachers of higher educational institutions of the country do not have special qualifications in teaching persons with special needs;

Today, for many people with special needs, university education should consist not only of acquiring relevant knowledge, but also of acquiring life and social skills, and higher education institutions, in turn, should be ready to provide this. In this regard, we believe that it is necessary to recognize the further development of inclusive education, strengthening the material and technical base of educational institutions as one of the priority tasks of the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and to create all conditions for the full implementation of the set tasks.

It should be noted that a number of positive trends are observed in this direction, the main of which is reflected in the practical actions of the

government to deepen reforms aimed at developing inclusive education in our country.

In particular:

A project to develop inclusive education is being implemented in our country with the funds raised by the Asian Development Bank, projects to strengthen the material and technical base of specialized boarding schools "Mehribonlik" and houses of mercy are being developed and implemented. "The problem of developing inclusive education in the Republic of Uzbekistan, supporting the rights and freedoms of persons with special educational needs is also reflected in the Strategy for the Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026. In particular, the 4th priority direction "Implementing a fair social policy, developing human capital", under Goal 66 "Forming an effective system of supporting persons with special educational needs, improving their quality and standard of life", directly envisages the protection and implementation of the rights to life of persons with special educational needs in our country. On December 3, 2021, on the occasion of the International Day of Persons with Special Educational Needs, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M.Mirziyoyev said: "Critical assessment of our work with the most socially vulnerable category of the population - persons with special educational needs, we are mobilizing all forces and opportunities so that they never feel alone and actively participate in state and economic life "we will continue" - they emphasized. This indicates that the leadership of Uzbekistan pays great attention to the legal protection of persons with special educational needs, their freedoms, as well as to the further development and improvement of the inclusive education system in our country. Based on the above, we consider the policy being implemented in our country to develop inclusion, which helps persons with special educational needs to lead a full-fledged lifestyle, lead an active life. participate in the economic and political life of society, as well as fulfill civic obligations, to be relevant and important in light of modern realities. Conclusions and proposals:

In the current realities of the socio-economic development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, taking into account the implementation of educational opportunities for persons with special educational needs, the inclusive education system in the republic is at its formation stage and needs to be supported by the state. Significant work is being carried out in Uzbekistan to create conditions for the living and education of persons with special educational needs, a legislative framework has been created to create conditions

for the further development of such categories of persons. In particular, the Concept for the Development of Inclusive Education in the Public Education System for 2020–2025 and the Concept for the Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 were adopted. In addition, the President of our country approved the Strategy for the Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2022–2026, aimed at creating a system of social support for persons with special educational needs and improving their quality of life and standard of living. Despite the achievements in the formation and implementation of inclusiveness in the higher education system of Uzbekistan, a number of problems have been identified, such as insufficient training of teaching staff for inclusive education, the architectural and engineering infrastructure of buildings does not meet the requirements of people with special needs, and the lack of special curricula adapted to inclusive education. In order to develop and effectively implement an inclusive education in higher education institutions of Uzbekistan, in our opinion, it would be appropriate to solve the following tasks:

Improving the legal framework of the inclusive model of education in accordance with the rules and principles of the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Special Needs; Harmonizing the system of collecting statistics and data on people with special needs based on generally recognized international definitions and tools;

Adapting new buildings and structures to the needs and requirements of people with special needs when constructing and reconstructing existing ones;

improving the system of training and advanced training of teachers directly involved in the inclusive education model;

Based on the capabilities of the republic and individual regions, with the active participation of social services in implementing programs for caring for and rehabilitating people with special needs, forming a system for monitoring the current state and development trends of inclusive education, training and employment in accordance with international standards and norms;

We believe that the implementation of these recommendations will help achieve the goals set out in the Concept for Reforming the Higher Education System until 2030 and implement reforms to effectively integrate, adapt and develop inclusive education in educational institutions.

The Program of Activities for Inclusive Education was adopted at the World Conference on Special Needs Education. The conference was held in Spain on June 7-10, 1994 in cooperation with UNESCO. Its purpose is to familiarize States,

international organizations, national aid organizations, non-governmental organizations and other sectors with the reforms and activities of implementing the Salamanca Declaration on the Practice, Reform and Principles of Special Needs Education.

The program is based on the experiences of the States participating in the conference and on the standard rules for the stabilization of the opportunities of persons with special needs, especially those with special needs. The right of every child to education is recognized in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights and reaffirmed in the Universal Declaration of Education for All. Every person with special needs has the right to express, if requested, his or her wishes in relation to the education he or she receives.

Parents have the right to receive advice on choosing a form of education that meets the wishes, conditions, and needs of their children. Inclusive education is an education system that is individualized and can be adapted to the needs of children and young people with special needs. This work is carried out in ordinary, normally developed children's educational institutions. To achieve this, it is necessary to have an individual approach to each child, create comfortable conditions for him based on his disability, and, if necessary, partially change the program and plan. A child with special needs attends a public kindergarten or school that is convenient for him, close to his home. The main work there is carried out by a teacher or class teacher.

In each preschool institution or school, there is a specially trained resource teacher, who advises and assists the group teacher: provides special educational equipment and supplies;

conducts explanatory work with parents and teachers: makes changes to the lesson schedule and program, if necessary, and justifies them;

improves the qualifications of teachers, enriches their knowledge;

organizes health care services, creates a favorable psychological environment.

Placing a child with a physical or mental disability in an ordinary kindergarten or school is the first step towards integration. There are different forms and levels of educational integration. In physical integration, the physical difference between a child with special needs and a healthy child should be reduced as much as possible.

A special class or department can be organized for this. In functional integration, the functional difference between a child with special needs and a healthy child should be eliminated as much as possible. For this, it is useful to

involve children with special needs in music, art, drama clubs, and sports. Social integration helps to reduce social differences, encourages children with special needs and normally developed children to make friends and treat each other with respect. It teaches normally developed children to be kind. Society should treat people with special needs correctly. All the provisions of our Constitution also apply to them. Any educational integration increases the quality of inclusive education.

The focus of inclusive education is on a child with a disability in physical or mental development, who is provided with comprehensive care. In the education system organized for children in need of special assistance, first of all, the child's requirements are studied. Positive aspects, abilities are taken into account, and shortcomings are observed. Certain conditions must be created in this education system. This includes modification, compensation, adaptation, and rehabilitation. For example, if a child does not hear, he or she can be provided with a hearing aid; cannot walk - it is necessary to provide a wheelchair for those who need special education, and if they cannot hold a simple spoon in their hands, they need to be provided with other convenient equipment. At a certain point in the school education process, many children have difficulties in learning, and at this time they need special education. Schools must find ways to provide effective education to all children. In particular, special education should be included in the general plan based on the agreements currently emerging for children with special needs. This led to the emergence of the concept of inclusive education. The biggest challenge in inclusive education is to form a "teaching methodology" of pedagogy for children with significant disadvantages, capable of effectively educating all children.

Integrated means an integral, inseparable part. Every child should be involved in education. In an integrated society, everyone has equal rights, it is a whole society. Thanks to inclusive education, society becomes an integrated society. Special needs education promotes the principles of effective pedagogy that benefits all children. It is accepted that people are different and, given the nature and stages of the learning process, the child should be adapted to the needs of the process, not the needs of the child. Child-centered pedagogy benefits all learners, including society. The acquired skills show that by ensuring that moderately high levels of success can be achieved, it is possible to reduce dropout and re-studies in the education system. Child-centered pedagogy helps to avoid wasting resources, which can result in poor quality education and a "one size fits all" mentality. In addition, inclusive education in educational

institutions for children with disabilities is carried out on the basis of the principles by which it can be organized.

Special education operates all over the world in the form of schools or boarding schools, as well as as small parts of general education schools. The education of children with special needs in the special education system makes it difficult for them to adapt to society after graduating from school. It also forces them to be away from their families. This category of children becomes accustomed to dependency, they face difficulties in serving themselves. In addition, many children with special needs are excluded from education. Currently, in our Republic, an inclusive education policy is being implemented in order to ensure that children in need of special assistance receive education in the special or general education system according to their level of development, characteristics of disabilities and abilities.

“Education shall be directed to the full development of the individual, to the development of his or her talents, mental and physical abilities, and to the preparation of the child for active participation in a free society.” Articles 2 and 28 relate to inclusive education, which stipulate that discrimination should be eliminated and that education should be accessible to all, in accordance with their abilities. The activities of children with special needs, other children, teachers and educators have a special place in inclusive education.

Thanks to such education, children with special needs: - satisfy their physical and mental needs;

- develop social behavior and self-service skills;
- master educational materials that take into account their capabilities;
- develop by participating in various games with their peers;
- can be a referee or goalkeeper in physical education classes, a timekeeper in various sports competitions;
- make friends in a friendly environment;
- participate in various entertainment and festive programs. Other children;
- create a friendly environment;
- take care of children with special needs, involve them in various games;
- participate in class events;
- ensure cleanliness and tidiness;
- develop a sense of responsibility for the team;
- participate in the preparation of didactic and play materials together;
- teachers and educators teach children to understand each other's inner worlds; - take into account the abilities and possibilities of each child;

- form life skills and independence in each child;
- analyze and evaluate work;
- provide practical assistance to parents;
- educate and educate all children equally;

Thus; inclusive education recognizes that children with special needs and special education can receive education not only in special schools, but also in general education schools where healthy children study.

Imam Bukhari (810–870) is a great scholar who received the honorable title "Amir al-Mu'minin in the science of Hadith". His narrations are of great importance for the education and upbringing of children in the family, family life and the benefit of society. Education begins from the day a child is born. Every child carefully observes the events and incidents that occur in his life. He imitates adults and strives to try every action himself. That is why every parent is required to lead an exemplary life and be an example and a lesson for his children in every way. Abu Isa Muhammad at-Tirmidhi (824–892). Known as an accomplished hadith scholar of his time, Abu Isa Muhammad at-Tirmidhi (824–892) has survived to this day most of the works attributed to him. The scholar's work "Al-Jami'" ("The Compiler") is the most famous of his works and is one of the collections of hadiths.

At-Tirmidhi says: "It is better for a person to raise his own child than to give charity every day," and with this advice he emphasizes that raising children in the family is the most meritorious work. In the work of Allama "Al-Jami", the Prophet Muhammad said to a person who was not able to take care of his children and was about to go to war: "Return to your children, for their upbringing is more meritorious." In another hadith, he emphasized: "A father cannot give his children anything better than good manners." Indeed, parents are role models for their children not only with their words, but also with their actions. The person with whom a child spends the most time, the child is most influenced and learns from. He absorbs the morality of that person, turns the mind and understanding in him into a motto for life. Raising a child is the most important task of the father and mother. Their every action, every word they say affects the upbringing of the child. Because the child imprints in his mind every event and incident he sees and hears in the family. For example, let's give an example of the relationship built throughout his life between a father and his child and analyze it. A child is born in a family, but when the child is born, the father is busy with meetings that he must attend and the work that needs to be done, he cannot get rid of his work. Days pass, when he takes his first steps, he is

on a business trip to another country, and when he learns a language, he is studying to improve his skills. Years pass and when he grows up a little, the child says to his father: "Daddy, I want to be like you."

Muloqot jarayonida bolalarning o'rtasida bir-birini tushunish, bir-biriga such qualities as helping, respecting are revealed. For example, children can interpret each other differently: it is unlikely that they will understand the goals, dreams and state of the interaction partner or not only understand, but also accept them. However, in both cases, the process of perception of a person by a person is manifested as an obligatory component of communication.

Perception. Before revealing the content of this aspect of communication, it is necessary to clarify the terms used. Often, the perception of a person by a person is considered as "social perception". The term "social perception" was first used in 1947 by J. Bruner as a new view of perception (New Looor). By social perception, the process of perception of social objects - other people, social groups, large social associations began to be understood. In the social psychological literature, this term is used in this context. Therefore, the perception of a person by a person, although it belongs to the sphere of social perception, does not fully cover it. If we imagine the processes of social perception in full, a complex and multifaceted scheme emerges. It includes not only the object, but also various variants of the subject of perception. If an individual is understood as a subject of perception, then he can perceive another individual belonging to his group, a "stranger" group. According to G.M. Andreeva, it is more appropriate to talk not about social perception in general, but about interpersonal perception or interpersonal perception. Russian psychologist A.A. Bodalyov, in his research, uses the expression "understanding another person" as a synonym for "perceiving another person". Understanding the term in such a broad sense is associated with the specific aspects of perceiving another person. Because perceiving another person means studying and describing the behavior of a child, not his physical state. Since a person is manifested as a person in the process of communication, he is also perceived as a person by another person, his communication partner. S.L. Rubinstein noted that based on the external appearance of behavior, we supposedly "read" another person, understand the content of his behavior. The impressions that arise in this process perform a management process in the process of communication.

7. The principle of competence

In classes where children with special needs are taught in an inclusive manner, highly qualified teachers are required to teach. In addition, an inclusive class teacher must also have advanced training in the field of defectology. The principles of organizing the educational process in schools (institutions) where inclusive education is introduced:

principles of special education;

corrective orientation;

a complex (clinical-genetic, neurophysiological, psychological-pedagogical) approach to identifying a defect, teaching;

determining the defective function on the ground. medical-psychological correction;

providing general secondary education, vocational guidance and preparation for social life;

differential-stratification and individual approach;

ensuring the continuity of education;

Inclusive education requires well-trained and qualified teachers. For this purpose, it is important to establish training programs that include children with different needs. However, training should not be too specialized. Because in a decentralized and integrated system, it is unrealistic for each school to have its own specialists. It is very important to use the existing staff to the fullest extent possible. Children with learning difficulties in inclusive education need generalist staff rather than specialists.

5.2. Guidelines for teaching inclusive education Inclusive education is, first of all, good general education and it includes the following: - Use everything you have. Try to use materials that arouse the child's interest. Offer multi-purpose applications that require the child to use their fingers and hands. Children learn through their 5 senses: sight, hearing, taste, smell, and touch. Therefore, it is advisable for the child to use applications that they can see, hear, taste, smell, and touch. - Analytical tasks. The task usually consists of many small tasks. There is no task that can be completed in one step. To ensure that the child successfully completes the exercise, divide the exercise into several small sections. - Sequence of exercises. Start with easy exercises. Then, as the child masters the previous exercise, the exercises become more difficult. - Variation. Serious exercises are alternated with organized free games and projects. - Do not isolate. Teaching a child individually does not mean isolating him. On the contrary, each exercise should be turned into a learning process in which all children can participate. We cannot say that no child knows everything perfectly

and cannot master everything in the same way. It is necessary to create opportunities for all classmates to help each other and provide them with support. – Simplify. Learning tasks should be as simple as possible. Make sure that your instructions are not misleading. Use a few words. Speak slowly and clearly. Do not just tell them to do something, but also show them how to do it. Each task in the tasks should be simple enough that the child can complete it independently.

Inclusive education ensures that people with special educational needs receive education on a par with their social peers, and (unless there are serious reasons for their development) they are accepted into regular schools. Children with severe disabilities are sometimes educated in special schools and special rehabilitation centers or in special classes at regular schools using corrective programs. Educational provision in these schools is necessarily provided taking into account the needs of the child.

The regular education process involves the organization of various forms of education together with the surrounding community, using individual correctional methods and adapted curricula, programs and other factors, based on the personal characteristics of the child with disabilities, and the use of special assistive devices (hearing aids, lenses, magnifying glasses, wheelchairs for those with special needs), various technical means and special visual aids. In turn, teachers of special educational institutions should act as local consultation departments and resource centers for general education students, parents, state and non-state community organizations.

The state should create the following conditions for the education of some children with special needs in general education institutions:

- early diagnosis of the need for special education;
- training of specialists;
- creation of all conditions (structures) adapted for those in need of special education when constructing buildings of general education institutions;
- increasing the network of rehabilitation centers for the implementation of correctional assistance;
- in order to organize the education of some children with special needs in general education, conducting advanced training courses for general education teachers, providing them with special aids, educational and methodological literature, methodological manuals, as well as organizing education at school using various programs.

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